

Research Trends in Plagiarism as visualized from SCOPUS

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ABSTRACT

Research is systematic and thorough investigation undertaken to discover new facts and information about a phenomenon. The flood of information on the Internet with the easy and speedy access has enabled the authors, researchers and students to download the web material modify and present it as their own work. Honesty, fairness and accountability are integral part of Academic pursuits of Teaching, Learning and Research. Unfair practices like Plagiarism adversely affects the ability, competence, inquire and analytical thinking of the researcher. It not only curbs originality and innovations but also hampers the process of research. It is a sheer bypassing of original author's efforts and intellectualism.

This review paper has explored various issues involved in Plagiarism. The paper has identified research productivity in plagiarism from 1993 to 2016 using SCOPUS as a bibliographic database. The paper also provided an insight into the citation overview of top 10 papers and the country where maximum research has been undertaken in this domain. It has also brought into focus the subject areas to which maximum authors have contributed.

The paper has examined earlier researches conducted on plagiarism. The tools and practices for deterring plagiarism discussed by various authors have been assessed theoretically.

As per the data revealed by SCOPUS all across the world there has been rapid increase in the research publications on deterrence of plagiarism but in India it has yet to take momentum. United States takes the lead in research productivity on plagiarism which is 52% of the total output as compared to India which is just 3.2%.

Keywords : Plagiarism; SCOPUS; Research Productivity

OBJECTIVES

- To examine the year wise research productivity in plagiarism in context to its awareness, tools/software, and policies.
- To find out the subject areas where the maximum authors have contributed.
- To identify the most preferred document type in which the research findings have been published.
- To determine nation wise research output.

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What is Plagiarism¹

Plagiarism comes from Latin word 'Plagiarius' meaning kidnapper and Greek word 'Plagium' meaning kidnapping. Plagiarism is the breach of trust. Plagiarism has plagued the academic world. It implies stealing one's idea and presenting them as their own. It questions the academic integrity intellectualism of those taking to it.

Few Definitions

Cambridge Dictionaries Online define Plagiarism as "to use another person's ideas or work and pretend that it is your own"²

Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines Plagiarism as "the act of using another person's words or ideas without giving credit to that person: the act of plagiarizing something"³

As per Reference Dictionary Plagiarism is "an act or instance of using or closely imitating the language and thoughts of another author without authorisation and the representation of that author's work as one's own, as by not crediting the original author."⁴

Reasons for plagiarism

- The flood of Information on the Internet and the easy and speedy access has enabled the students to download Web material, modify it and present it as their own work.
- The common trend of bringing computers to academic places has made cutting and pasting much easier than putting into words one's own ideas.
- To make it worse speed brought by cutting edge technology makes students casual in writing.
- Lack of consistency in citation is also a problem.
- Failure to report such cases to the authorities concerned, pulls and pressures of consumerist Society etc. are the leading causes of plagiarism.
- Students plagiarise due to laziness, fear or extreme pressure to perform.
- Ignorance about plagiarism is also prevalent.
- Lack of proper time management skills forces them to adopt this cut and paste technique.

Review of Literature

Culwin, F. and Lancaster, T. (2001)⁵ has discussed Plagiarism issues for Higher Education. Expedition access provided by the Internet has enabled the researchers to download the material and present it as their own. This practice adversely affects their ability, competence, inquire and analyze. In short cheating culture is evolving. Institutions across the globe are looking for technical solutions to implement their Anti-Plagiarism policy. The author suggested a four stage Plagiarism detection Model in his work. First is the collection

stage in which students submit their work to the system via Web. In the Detection stage, the collected work is run through the detection engine where a list of similar submissions is produced. This is followed by human led stage of confirmation. The final stage is that of decision making. With evidence students have to be assured that they have committed an academic offense. The use of automated system to check plagiarism is increasingly being used. It has to be analysed why the students resort to this practice. Another problem is that of consistency. Some Institutions have pro-active, some have reactive Anti-Plagiarism Policy. To eliminate the culture, the standards across the education sector need to be consistent. Along with this motivating the students efficient policy on plagiarism and data protection, copyright should be there. Designing specified courses and assignments can also help.

Bruton, S and Childers, D (2015)⁶ focused on the faculty views on student plagiarism in their work. University Faculty have divergent views on Plagiarism and the ways to curb it. Caused mainly due to laziness, it can be controlled by engaging the students in written assignments and by promoting moral academic values. Most of them are in favour of Turnitin- an Anti-Plagiarism Software. The authors conducted the survey to observe attitude towards Turnitin. Interviews were held with faculty members across various disciplines. Drafting and implementing Anti-Plagiarism Policy, creating awareness by taking librarians into confidence can help in doing away with this culture.

Caruana, A. and others (2000)⁷ in their work "The Effect of Anomie on Academic Dishonesty among University Students" discussed that academic dishonesty has become the order of the day. Business students accounted for the most of it as found amongst top 31 Universities. 'Anomie' means the absence of law. It is also referred to as Incompetence, Inability and Wickedness. Time deficit pressure to perform make the students weak. Further casual attitude of faculty make students plagiarise. The authors conducted the survey among the students of Australian University. It was found that male students are more likely to Plagiarise. Major limitations of this study that the students are likely to under report their chance of cheating despite assurance of anonymity.

Lampert, L.D. (2004)⁸ in his work "Integrating Discipline based anti-plagiarism instruction into the information literacy curriculum" discussed the collaboration of Librarians and faculty members. Librarians and faculty members often face Orwellian Practice. Plagiarism is conveniently forgotten. High profile cases of Plagiarism in Journalism have come to light. It is important for Librarians and Faculty Members to discuss the ways of curbing Plagiarism. Students should be apprised about the proper citations style and ethics. There should be greater collaboration between Librarians and Faculty Members. In Information Literacy sessions should be organized in which education regarding meaning of Plagiarism, style format, code of ethics, requisite standards should be imparted. Students

should be involved to develop their own understanding of Plagiarism. A culture where chances of cheating are eliminated should be evolved.

Nisha, F and others (2015)⁹ in their work “Plagiarism in Research: special reference to initiatives taken by Indian Organisation” highlighted various Plagiarism detection tools and steps taken by various institutions in dealing with this malpractice.

Tripathi, Richa and others (2015)¹⁰ focussed on various freely available online Plagiarism Detection tools/software. The paper has also highlighted the benefits and drawbacks of the Anti-plagiarism tools/software.

Chakravarty, Rupak and Mahajan, Preeti (2014)¹¹ in their paper have discussed plagiarism as a grave epidemic. As per the authors it is affecting not only academics but also other areas where content creation is involved. It happens when the views, thoughts of other person is copied in an unattributed way. Beginning with the definitions the authors have brilliantly described the causes and measures to check plagiarism. Authors opine that before Internet, plagiarism was not that easy to do and detect as a lot of labour was required in it but in the current times various plagiarism software and web based tools have been devised for the same. They have explained some of the freely available plagiarism detection software like 'Open Access Plagiarism Research', 'Duplichecker', 'Plagiarism Checker' and special emphasis has been given to Turnitin a commercial online plagiarism detection tool as it has been installed in Panjab University and is being used successfully. The authors have concluded the paper with the suggestions that librarians, teachers, researchers as well as students must do something to curb this menace. Teachers should be entrusted with the task of apprising the students about proper paraphrasing and giving due acknowledgement to the original author. Training and awareness programmes should be organised to spread awareness and prevent the spread of this ill practice.

Methodology and Data Source

The present Study reviews the publications Output of research publication on plagiarism 1993 to 2016. The publication data was procured from Scopus which is an International multidisciplinary bibliographical Database covering 53 million records, more than 22000 titles and 5000 publishers. It is a product of Elsevier and is the considered world's largest indexing and abstracting database and offers citation searching. Launched in 2004, it provides access to Science-Technology-Medicine (STM) literature with a limited coverage of Social Science and Arts and Humanities.

Database search was undertaken on June 6, 2016 by using the Boolean operators 'and' and 'or' between the terms Plagiarism/Librarians/Libraries/Library. The results were downloaded under various headings like Year, Author, Number of publications, Document type and citation overview. The whole data was exported to MS-Excel format.

Figure 1 Growth of Publications in Plagiarism

Figure 1 shows the growth of publications in the field of plagiarism. The data retrieved from SCOPUS ranges from 1993 to 2016. For analysis the authors have divided this period into 4 groups of 5 years each and the year 2016 has also been taken into consideration. As per the figure the least productive span was from 1993-1998 contributing only 4.4% to the research productivity. The most productive period was 2010-16 recording 57%. The maximum growth happened in 2005-10 with 4 times increase in the percentage of publications.

Figure 2 Document Type

A look on the figure 2 shows that research findings take the form of articles. 55.7% of the Research findings have been published in the form of articles. After the articles, researchers also prefer Conference Proceedings for their research publications which accounted for 22.8% of the total productivity.

Figure 3 Nation wise Publication Output

The figure 3 reveals that maximum research papers on plagiarism have been published in United States with 52% of the total output. This is followed by United Kingdom and Germany with 5.3% of the total output. India holds the fourth position with 3.2% of the total output. Rest of the 33 Nations contributes 34.2% of the total output.

Figure 4 Subject wise Research Productivity

The Subject wise distribution of publications is listed in Figure 4. Social sciences emerged as the front ranker in terms of publications of literature on Plagiarism with 44.5% of the total articles as retrieved by SCOPUS. It is followed by Computer Science with 20%, Engineering with 9.5% and Medicine with 7.1%.

YEAR OF PUBLICATION	DOCUMENT TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL TITLE	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	TOTAL
2006	Health information literacy and competencies of information age students: Results from the interactive online Research Readiness Self-Assessment (RRSA)	Ivanitskaya L., O'Boyle L., Casey A.M., Ivanitskaya L.	Journal of Medical Internet Research	7	8	8	15	2	40
2007	Institutional repositories: Evaluating the reasons for non-use of Cornell University's installation of DSpace	Davis P.M., Connolly M.J.L.	D-Lib Magazine	8	7	13	10	1	39
1997	CHECK: A document plagiarism detection system	Si A., Leong H.V., Lau R.W.H.	Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Applied Computing	5	7	6	3	3	24
2001	Mouse click plagiarism: The role of technology in plagiarism and the librarian's role in combating it	Auer N.J., Krupar E.M.	Library Trends	7	3	2	0	.1	13
2004	Academic original sin: Plagiarism, the internet, and librarians	Wood G.	Journal of Academic Librarianship	1	4	5	1	0	11
2010	Deconstructing plagiarism: International students and textual borrowing practices	Amsberry D.	Reference Librarian	2	3	1	3	1	10
2007	Plagiarism detection without reference collections	Meyer Zu Eissen S., Stein B., Kulig M.	Studies in Classification, Data Analysis, Knowledge Organization	3	1	1	3	1	9
1993	Difficulties and characteristics of students from developing countries in using American libraries	Liu Z.	College and Research Libraries	3	3	1	2	0	9
2008	Electronic theses and dissertation (ETD) repositories: What are they? Where do they come from? How do they work?	Yiotis K.	OCLC Systems and Services	0	2	4	1	1	8
2006	Plagiarism on the rise	Boisvert R.F., Irwin M.J.	Communications of the ACM	2	1	2	0	0	5

Table 1: Citation Overview of top 10 papers

The above Table depicts the Citation Overview of top 10 papers from 2012-2016 without taking into consideration the year of publication of respective document title.

CONCLUSION

Ethics and honesty are the very basis of academics. In teaching and research, there is no room for dishonesty. It adversely affects intellectualism, career and reputation of the researchers. Transparency is the basis of research which begins after thorough analysis of the work done before. In writing research papers due acknowledgement to previous authors and their works should be given. Even UGC¹² emphasizes on regulatory mechanism for preventing plagiarism in higher educational institutions for all categories. In order to ensure intellectual fairness different levels of punishment have been recommended by UGC which should be implemented earnestly. Full implementation of anti-plagiarism policies formulated by the Institutions will also help them in this task.

ENDNOTES

1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plagiarism> (Accessed on 16-05-2016)
2. <http://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/plagiarize?q=plagiarism> (Accessed on 16-05-2016)

3. <http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/plagiarism> (Accessed on 16-05-2016)
4. <http://www.wordreference.com/definition/plagiarism> (Accessed on 16-05-2016)
5. Culwin, Fintan and Lancaster, Thomas (2001) "Plagiarism issues for Higher Education" *VINE*, 31 (2), pp36-41
<http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/abs/10.1108/03055720010804005?journalCode=vine> (Accessed on 6-06-2016)
6. Bruton, Samuel and Schilders, Dan (2016), "The ethics and politics of policing plagiarism: a qualitative study of faculty views on student plagiarism and Turnitin" *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 41 (2), 2016.
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02602938.2015.1008981> (Accessed on 10-06-2016)
7. Caruana, Albert and others (2000), "The effect of anomie on academic dishonesty among university students" *International Journal of Educational Management*, 14 (1), pp. 23-30 <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/abs/10.1108/09513540010310378> (Accessed on 13-05-2016)
8. Lampert, Lynn D (2004), "Integrating discipline-based anti-plagiarism instruction into the information literacy curriculum" *Reference Services Review*. 32 (4), pp.347-355
<http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/abs/10.1108/00907320410569699> (Accessed on 16-06-2016)
9. Nisha, F and others (2015), "Plagiarism in Research: Special Reference to initiatives taken by Indian Organisations" *Emerging Trends and Technologies in Libraries and Information Services (EETLIS)*, pp.281-284
<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=7048212&isnumber=7048153> (Accessed on 06-07-2016)
10. Tripathi, R. (2015), "Avoiding plagiarism in research through free online plagiarism tools," *Emerging Trends and Technologies in Libraries and Information Services (EETLIS)*, pp. 275-280
<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=7048211&isnumber=7048153> (Accessed on 26-06-2016)
11. Chakravarty, Rupak and Mahajan, Preeti (2014), "Understanding, Detecting & Preventing Plagiarism: Effective Tools & Measures" In *Proceedings of the 59th ILA International Conference, Organized by MGCL IIT Roorkee and Indian Library Association (ILA)*. 22-24 February 2014.
12. UGC Draft on Plagiarism.
https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/8864815_UGC-Public-Notice-on-Draft-UGC-Regulations,-2017.pdf